

Exploring ASEAN Integration through the Experiences of Generation Z in Phnom Penh, Cambodia

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Abstract

The Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) has played a pivotal role in promoting Cambodia's economic, political, and social cooperation with other member nations. Despite this, little is known about how Cambodian Generation Z—a dynamic group shaping the future of the country—is contributing to national development. This article investigates experience with ASEAN integration among Generation Z in Phnom Penh, Cambodia, using a mixed-methods approach. The research comprises eight key informant interviews and a survey of 414 participants. Results indicate that Generation Z in Phnom Penh possess limited experience with ASEAN integration. Most respondents have little experience with ASEAN-related events including travel, direct contact with ASEAN people, or chances like regional job markets and scholarships. Nevertheless, experiences related to cultural exchange, ASEAN identity growth, and optimistic attitudes toward ASEAN integration are more moderate, though not commonly shared. Though they are not common, a smaller number of respondents indicated more deep experiences via participating in different exchange programs, ASEAN simulations, and leadership projects. The study indicates that in order to improve practical experience and strengthen knowledge of regional integration, ASEAN projects need more active involvement of young people.

Keywords: *ASEAN Integration, Generation Z, Experience, Phnom Penh, Youth Awareness.*

JEL Classification codes: *F02, F53*

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Introduction

Founded on August 8, 1967, by Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore, and Thailand, the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) is a regional intergovernmental organisation. Later, it grew to include Cambodia, Myanmar, Laos, Vietnam, and Brunei, becoming a ten-member group dedicated to fostering economic development, political cooperation, regional peace and stability, and socio-cultural development (ASEAN, 2021). ASEAN has become a significant force

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in both regional and global politics over the years, with an increasing emphasis on the development of a sense of shared identity and community among its diverse populations.

Having joined ASEAN in 1999, Cambodia has been actively involved in promoting the objectives of the association. Being a developing country, Cambodia sees ASEAN integration as a strategic tool to improve regional connections, draw investment, and assist national growth. The extent to which ordinary Cambodians—especially young people—are aware of and involved with ASEAN projects still lacks study.

The future of ASEAN depends much on young people. Emerging leaders' views, experiences, and degrees of involvement in ASEAN integration are vital for the long-term development of the region. Generation Z—those born between the mid-1990s and early 2010s—makes up a big and growingly powerful population in Cambodia. In this situation, urban youth—especially in Phnom Penh—are particularly well positioned. Phnom Penh, the political, economic, and educational centre of the nation, offers more exposure to worldwide and regional events, hence its youthful population is a key group for grasping grassroots views of ASEAN.

Although the discussions on youth and regionalism have been increasing, there is still a dearth of literature that delves into the lived experiences of young people in Southeast Asia, particularly in Cambodia, and how they see ASEAN integration. Little attention has been given to young views in most current studies, which mostly concentrate on high-level policy or economic aspects. This void highlights the need of studies that record the everyday experiences and perspectives of young people in relation to ASEAN.

In order to fill this void, this article delves into the experiences of Generation Z in Phnom Penh in relation to ASEAN integration. It seeks to understand how this generation is aware of, and involved with, ASEAN, as well as the social, educational, and cultural factors that influence their perspectives. By concentrating on urban Cambodian youth, this study adds to a more realistic picture of ASEAN integration as seen through the eyes of its future stewards.

Methodology

Research Design and Instruments

This research uses a mixed-methods research methodology to thoroughly investigate Generation Z's experiences of ASEAN integration by combining statistical and qualitative techniques. By integrating the breadth of quantitative data with the depth of qualitative insights, this strategy provides for a richer and more nuanced understanding of the study topic (Creswell, 2014).

A quantitative survey was conducted using a standardised questionnaire. It aims to collect data from a larger group of people so the researcher can assess the levels of experiences of ASEAN integration among a representative sample. The survey is intended to allow statistical analysis to find trends, patterns, and possible correlations between variables by means of close-ended questions matching the research objective. This method guarantees objectivity, generalisability, and the capacity to evaluate the research hypotheses.

Along with the quantitative data, the qualitative method uses a Key Informant Interview (KII) approach. Participants are chosen to offer in-depth analysis of their own experiences, attitudes, and opinions about ASEAN integration. This qualitative method lets the researcher explore more deeply into contextual elements and reveal the nuances underlying the quantitative results. While keeping attention on the study objectives, the semi-structured interview method offers flexibility. This guarantees a balance between directed investigation and the appearance of unanticipated ideas, therefore enhancing the whole study.

This study is especially well-suited to the mixed-methods technique, which combines the advantages of both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The quantitative survey gives assessable data on the levels of experiences; the qualitative interviews provide contextual experiences and let one discern underlying meanings and motivations. Mix-methods approach guarantees the reliability and validity of the data collection for the extensiveness of the results, and the method catches both the "what" and the "why" of the investigated phenomenon, hence improving the validity and comprehensiveness of the results (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2010).

Statistical and Qualitative Data Analysis Tools

Statistical Tools

Descriptive statistics were used to summarise and characterise the demographic data of respondents, hence generating findings as frequencies and percentages. Likert-scale item mean and standard deviation were computed to evaluate core tendencies and the variety of respondent opinions and experiences (Field, 2018).

Qualitative Data Analysis Tools

The qualitative data collected via Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) was analysed using the following tools and techniques:

Coding: Qualitative data was carefully categorised and organised into meaningful units using open and axial coding methods. Codes were generated inductively from the participants' replies and matched with the study goals to guarantee a thorough understanding of the data (Charmaz, 2014).

Thematic Analysis: Patterns or themes within the qualitative data were identified, analysed, and reported using a thematic analysis method. This approach guaranteed in-depth interpretation of the participants' narratives, hence offering insightful analysis of their experiences of ASEAN integration (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

Sample Size and Sampling Method

Sample Size

Cochran's method was used to determine the sample size for this study, hence guaranteeing statistical reliability and representativeness of the results. The calculation was made in accordance with the following parameters:

Population size: The projected Phnom Penh Generation Z population (unknown).

Confidence level: 95% (The common practice)

Margin of error: $\pm 4.82\%$ (Usually set at 5%)

Response distribution: 50% (assumed for maximum variability, as the definite proportion is unknown)

Based on these parameters, 382 respondents were the calculated sample size. Nevertheless, the reliability of the findings was further enhanced by the successful collection of data from 414 respondents. The experiences of Generation Z in Phnom Penh regarding ASEAN integration are analysed using a robust dataset which this sample size provides.

Sampling Method

Research Survey Respondents: The study used a non-probability convenience sampling method to collect data. Potential respondents were given a Google Docs survey link via Telegram platform. This method sought voluntary participation, in which they were encouraged to fill out the survey at their convenience. Despite these limitations, the method best fits the study's focus on Generation Z, who can communicate quickly and effectively through Telegram platform.

Key Informant Interview participants: Participants in the Key Informant Interviews (KII) are selected using purposive sampling, a non-probability selection methodology commonly used in qualitative research (Patton, 2015). This approach was used to guarantee that participants had particular qualities pertinent to the study—specifically, being Generation Z members living in Phnom Penh. These people were selected as their experiences about ASEAN integration are crucial for fulfilling the study goals.

Purposive sampling lets one choose information-rich individuals who can offer thorough and nuanced perspectives on the phenomena under study (Creswell & Poth, 2018). The research intends to collect in-depth data that helps to fully comprehend the subject by emphasizing people who fit the established criteria.

Qualitative research ideas, which stress depth of inquiry above large sample numbers, underlie the choice to involve eight people for the KIIs. Sample size in qualitative research is usually defined by the idea of data saturation—the point at which more data no longer produces fresh insights or themes (Guest, Bunce, & Johnson, 2006).

Previous studies indicate that when the sample is well chosen and the interview procedure is comprehensive, significant themes can sometimes arise with a small number of participants (Baker & Edwards, 2012). For this study, a sample size of eight individuals is deemed adequate for many reasons; The study is to investigate particular experiences of Generation Z in Phnom Penh pertaining to ASEAN integration. A smaller, more focused sample allows one thoroughly investigate these trends. Less people are required to reflect the diversity of experiences and viewpoints inside this group because all participants come from the same demographic cohort and geographic area.

The study guarantees a balance between complete data and practicality by involving eight carefully chosen individuals, hence conforming with qualitative research best practices. This strategy will help to produce strong insights on how ASEAN integration is seen and experienced by Generation Z in Phnom Penh.

Research’s Pilot

A reliability study of the 10 items measuring Generation Z’s experiences on ASEAN integration is presented in Table 1 below. The questions used a five-point Likert scale, with 1 denoting "No Experience" and 5 denoting "Extensive Experience." The scale's Cronbach's alpha coefficient, as demonstrated by the results, was 0.922, indicating a very high degree of internal consistency among the items. This indicated that the scale was excellently reliable and the items measured the same construct, and so all of the 10 items was retained in the scale to capture the experiences of the Generation Z on ASEAN integration.

Table 1. Chronbach’s Alpha Test on 10 Items about the Generation Z experiences in ASEAN Integration

Variables	Chronbach’s	No. of Items	Reliability
Experiences in ASEAN Integration	0.922	10	Excellent

Note: Respondents’ Profile (Sample size, n=414)

As stated in table 2, the demographic profile of the respondents reflects a diverse group of Generation Z in Phnom Penh engaged with ASEAN integration. The majority of respondents are female, with a significant portion identifying as male. Age-wise, the largest group falls within the

19-21 age range, followed by those in the 22-24 age group, while a smaller proportion are in the 25-28 range.

In terms of education, most are currently pursuing a Bachelor's degree, with a notable number already having completed their undergraduate studies. A smaller percentage is enrolled in graduate studies. When it comes to employment, over half are employed in some capacity, while a significant portion remains in education. Social media usage is high, with most respondents using social media daily, indicating a strong influence of digital platforms on their views about ASEAN integration.

Overall, the respondents represent a broad spectrum of Generation Z Cambodians in Phnom Penh with varied educational backgrounds, employment statuses, and levels of social media engagement, offering a comprehensive view of their knowledge and perspectives on ASEAN integration.

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage of Demographic Data

Age Bracket	Frequency	Percentage
25-28	54	23.89%
22-24	73	32.30%
19-21	82	36.28%
Gender		
Male	133	32.13%
Female	281	67.87%
Educational Attainment		
Completed Graduate School (GS) Studies	17	4.10%
Currently Attending GS Studies	80	19.32%
Completed Bachelor's Degree	97	23.44%
Currently Taking Bachelor's Degree	206	49.76%
Completed High School	11	2.66%
Did Not Complete High School	1	0.24%
Others	2	0.49%
Work Status		
Employed (Full-time, part-time, Self-employed)	239	57.72%
Unemployed (Not studying)	8	1.93%
Student (Not Currently Working)	157	37.93%
Others (working and studying)	10	2.41%
Social Media Usage		
Daily	258	62.32%
Weekly	41	9.90%
Occasionally	107	55.84%
Never	8	1.94%

KII Participants' Profile

Table 3 presents the profiles of the eight participants involved in the Key Informant Interviews (KII), offering a glimpse into their demographics, current activities, and social media usage patterns for regional news updates. The participants, primarily young adults, reflect a mix of students and working individuals, with a majority being female. Their varying engagement with social media for news consumption highlights the role of digital platforms in staying informed about regional developments.

Participant 1, a 22-year-old female, is currently working but not studying. She uses social media almost every day to access regional news updates, indicating a high level of engagement with digital platforms for staying informed. Her profile suggests a balance between professional responsibilities and active news consumption.

Participant 2, a 21-year-old female, is currently studying but not working. She uses social media "usually" to get regional news updates, reflecting a moderate level of engagement. As a student, her reliance on social media for news may align with her academic or personal interests in staying updated on regional affairs.

Participant 3, a 20-year-old female, is both studying and working. She uses social media "occasionally" for regional news updates, suggesting a more selective or limited engagement with digital news sources. Her dual commitments may influence the frequency of her social media usage for news.

Participant 4, a 20-year-old female, is currently studying but not working. She uses social media every day to access regional news updates, indicating a consistent and habitual reliance on digital platforms for staying informed. Her profile reflects a strong connection to social media as a primary news source.

Participant 5, a 22-year-old female, is also studying but not working. Like Participant 4, she uses social media every day for regional news updates, underscoring the importance of digital platforms in her daily routine for staying informed.

Participant 6, a 24-year-old female, is currently working but not studying. She uses social media "usually" to get regional news updates, suggesting a balanced approach to news consumption alongside her professional responsibilities.

Participant 7, a 23-year-old male, is currently studying but not working. He uses social media every day for regional news updates, highlighting a consistent and frequent engagement with digital news sources. His profile reflects a strong reliance on social media for staying informed.

Participant 8, a 23-year-old male, is currently working but not studying. He also uses social media every day to access regional news updates, indicating a high level of engagement with digital platforms for news consumption. His profile aligns with the trend of daily social media usage for staying updated.

Collectively, the participants represent a young, predominantly female group with varying levels of engagement in education and employment. Their reliance on social media for regional news updates ranges from occasional to daily use, reflecting the diverse ways in which digital platforms are integrated into their lives for staying informed. The data suggests that social media plays a significant role in how this demographic accesses and consumes regional news, with daily usage being a common pattern among most participants. This highlights the growing influence of digital platforms as a primary source of information for young adults in the region.

Table 3. KII Participants' Profile

KII Participant	Age	Gender	Currently Studying	Currently Working	Frequency of Using Social Media to Get Some Regional News Update
Participant 1	22	Female	No	Yes	Almost everyday
Participant 2	21	Female	Yes	No	Usually
Participant 3	20	Female	Yes	Yes	Occasionally
Participant 4	20	Female	Yes	No	Everyday
Participant 5	22	Female	Yes	No	Everyday
Participant 6	24	Female	No	Yes	Usually
Participant 7	23	Male	Yes	No	Everyday
Participant 8	23	Male	No	Yes	Everyday
				Total : 8 KII Participants	

Results

Experiences of Generation Z in Phnom Penh about ASEAN Integration

Table 4. presents the findings on the experiences of Generation Z in Phnom Penh with ASEAN integration, based on a quantitative survey.

The overall General Weighted Average for Generation Z's experiences with ASEAN integration is 2.56, which falls under the category of "Very Little Experience," with a standard deviation of 0.30. This indicates that, on average, respondents have limited practical experiences with ASEAN integration, reflecting that their engagement with ASEAN-related opportunities and activities is relatively low.

Among the specific experience items, the lowest mean score (1.81) is observed in "I have traveled to other ASEAN countries for study, work, or leisure purposes," categorized as "Very Little Experience" with a standard deviation of 1.12. This suggests that the majority of respondents have had very few opportunities to visit other ASEAN countries, whether for academic, professional, or personal reasons.

Similarly, "I have interacted with people from other ASEAN countries in person or online" also received a low mean score (2.40, SD = 1.19), indicating limited interactions with individuals from other ASEAN nations. While some respondents may have had online or in-person exchanges, the overall experience remains minimal.

Other items reflecting "Very Little Experience" include "I have participated in activities or events related to ASEAN integration, such as seminars, workshops, festivals, or competitions" (2.20, SD = 1.10) and "I have benefited from the opportunities and resources offered by ASEAN integration, such as scholarships, grants, jobs, or markets" (2.07, SD = 1.10). These findings suggest that Generation Z in Phnom Penh has not been highly involved in ASEAN-related events or benefited significantly from the opportunities provided by ASEAN integration.

On the other hand, there are several items with slightly more moderate experience levels. "I have learned about the cultures and histories of other ASEAN countries" has a mean score of 2.84, which indicates "Moderate Experience" with a standard deviation of 1.02. This suggests that while the respondents have engaged to some extent with the cultural and historical aspects of ASEAN countries, the experience is not widespread across all participants. Similarly, "I have developed a sense of cultural and social identity as a Cambodian and an ASEAN citizen" (2.65, SD = 1.06) and "I have increased my awareness and appreciation of the diversity and commonality of ASEAN countries and cultures" (2.67, SD = 1.08) indicate that respondents have some experience in forming an ASEAN-related identity and recognizing cultural diversity, though again, these experiences are not universally strong.

Other items that fall under "Moderate Experience" include "I have improved my attitude and motivation towards ASEAN integration and its goals and values" (2.74, SD = 1.05), which shows a somewhat positive but limited shift in attitudes towards ASEAN integration, and "I have enhanced my skills and competencies to cope with the demands and expectations of ASEAN integration, such as communication, collaboration, or problem-solving" (2.51, SD = 1.10), which suggests some engagement with the skills necessary for ASEAN integration, albeit not extensively.

The standard deviation values across the experience items range from 1.02 to 1.19, indicating a moderate level of variability in respondents' experiences. The relatively high standard deviations suggest differing levels of exposure and engagement, with some respondents having more experiences than others.

The findings suggest that Generation Z in Phnom Penh has "Very Little Experience" with ASEAN integration, especially in terms of travel, direct interaction, and tangible benefits. However, they do

have moderate experiences in cultural learning, developing a sense of identity, and increasing awareness of ASEAN's diversity. This indicates that while their direct engagement with ASEAN integration is limited, there is some exposure to its broader cultural and social dimensions.

Table 4. Generation Z in Phnom Penh's Experiences about ASEAN Integration

Perception Items	Mean	Description	SD
1. I have travelled to other ASEAN countries for study, work, or leisure purposes.	1.81	Very Little Experience	1.12
2. I have interacted with people from other ASEAN countries in person or online.	2.40	Very Little Experience	1.19
3. I have learned about the cultures and histories of other ASEAN countries.	2.84	Moderate Experience	1.02
4. I have participated in activities or events related to ASEAN integration, such as seminars, workshops, festivals, or competitions.	2.20	Very Little Experience	1.10
5. I have benefited from the opportunities and resources offered by ASEAN integration, such as scholarships, grants, jobs, or markets.	2.07	Very Little Experience	1.10
6. I have faced some challenges or difficulties due to ASEAN integration, such as language barriers, cultural conflicts, or competition.	2.01	Very Little Experience	1.09
7. I have developed a sense of cultural and social identity as a Cambodian and an ASEAN citizen.	2.65	Moderate Experience	1.06
8. I have enhanced my skills and competencies to cope with the demands and expectations of ASEAN integration, such as communication, collaboration, or problem-solving.	2.51	Very Little Experience	1.10
9. I have increased my awareness and appreciation of the diversity and commonality of ASEAN countries and cultures.	2.67	Moderate Experience	1.08
10. I have improved my attitude and motivation towards ASEAN integration and its goals and values.	2.74	Moderate Experience	1.05
General Weighted Average	2.56	Very Little Experience	0.30

To further validate the survey findings on Gen Z's direct experiences with ASEAN integration, key informant interviews (KII) were conducted to explore how young Cambodians engage with ASEAN initiatives and programs. Table 4 presents key themes emerging from the interviews, providing insights into their lived experiences in ASEAN-related activities. The responses highlight diverse engagements, from participation in academic and cultural exchanges to leadership in regional initiatives.

Participation in ASEAN Programs: Engaging with the Region. A significant number of participants (P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, P8) reported having first-hand experience with ASEAN-related programs, such as leadership summits, student exchanges, and regional conferences. These programs provided them with opportunities to interact with peers from different ASEAN countries, enhancing their understanding of regional cooperation and fostering a sense of belonging within ASEAN.

Academic & Cultural Exchange: Strengthening Regional Connections. Several respondents (P3, P4, P6, P7, P8) shared experiences of participating in ASEAN academic and cultural exchange programs. Some engaged in student research collaborations with peers from Vietnam and Indonesia, while others joined cultural exchange events organized by international schools in

Cambodia. These experiences helped them develop cross-cultural awareness and strengthen ties with fellow ASEAN youth, reinforcing the role of ASEAN in promoting regional solidarity.

ASEAN Simulations & Model Summits: Experiencing Diplomacy Firsthand. Another common experience among participants (P2, P5, P8) was their involvement in ASEAN simulation activities, where they took on roles as diplomats or policymakers in model summits. These simulations allowed them to discuss and negotiate solutions to regional challenges, providing a practical understanding of ASEAN's decision-making processes and the complexities of regional diplomacy.

Workshops on ASEAN Issues: Learning from Experts. Some participants (P1, P2, P3, P7) attended expert-led workshops focusing on ASEAN-related topics such as artificial intelligence, economic integration, and political cooperation. These workshops deepened their awareness of regional trends and challenges, offering them insights beyond what they had learned in formal education.

Youth Leadership and Advocacy: ASEAN as a Platform for Change. Several participants (P6, P8) took on leadership roles in ASEAN-affiliated initiatives, including entrepreneurship programs, environmental advocacy, and social innovation projects. One respondent participated in a social entrepreneurship program in South Korea, collaborating with young innovators from other ASEAN countries. Another respondent led an initiative on circular economy solutions, working with youth leaders from Myanmar, Indonesia, and the Philippines. These experiences demonstrated ASEAN's potential as a platform for youth-driven change.

Policy Engagement & Debate: Addressing ASEAN's Regional Challenges. A few respondents (P5, P8) were actively involved in ASEAN-related policy discussions. One participant attended a conference on the South China Sea dispute, engaging in debates about ASEAN's role in regional security. Another participant debated ASEAN's non-interference policy in relation to the Myanmar crisis. These experiences provided them with a deeper understanding of ASEAN's political and security dimensions.

Environmental & Social Initiatives: Tackling Regional Issues through ASEAN. ASEAN integration also served as a platform for youth involvement in environmental and social initiatives. A participant (P6) shared their experience working on a cross-border climate change awareness project, collaborating with ASEAN peers to develop sustainability solutions. This highlights ASEAN's role in fostering regional cooperation beyond economic and political matters.

Barriers to ASEAN Engagement: Limited Accessibility and Exposure. Despite the positive experiences shared by many participants, some respondents (P1, P2) noted challenges in accessing ASEAN-related programs. Limited awareness of available opportunities was a recurring issue, with many Cambodian students unaware of how to engage with ASEAN initiatives. This suggests a need for greater outreach efforts to ensure more young Cambodians can participate in and benefit from ASEAN integration.

General Insights: ASEAN Integration as a Lived Experience. In summary, the key informant interviews revealed that Gen Z in Phnom Penh is actively engaging with ASEAN integration through academic exchanges, policy simulations, leadership initiatives, and environmental projects. While many participants recognized the benefits of these experiences in fostering personal and professional growth, some also highlighted challenges related to limited accessibility. Their stories offer a unique perspective on how ASEAN integration is not just an abstract concept but a tangible force shaping the lives of Cambodian youth.

As ASEAN continues to develop, ensuring greater inclusivity and accessibility for young people will be crucial in strengthening regional cooperation and fostering a deeper sense of ASEAN identity among the next generation.

Table 5. Thematic Summary Matrix on KII Participants' Experiences about ASEAN Integration

Theme	Description	Participants Mentioning Theme
Participation in ASEAN Programs	Respondents have joined ASEAN-related programs such as conferences, workshops, academic exchanges, and leadership initiatives.	P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, P8
Academic & Cultural Exchange	Experiences with ASEAN integration primarily involve interactions with students from other ASEAN countries through study programs, research, and academic simulations.	P3, P4, P6, P7, P8
ASEAN Simulation & Model Summits	Several participants took part in ASEAN model summits, where they acted as delegates to debate regional issues and learn about ASEAN diplomacy.	P2, P5, P8
Workshops on ASEAN Issues	Some participants attended ASEAN workshops covering topics such as artificial intelligence (AI), diplomacy, and regional cooperation.	P1, P2, P3, P7
Youth Leadership & Advocacy	Participants engaged in leadership roles within ASEAN initiatives, including entrepreneurship, environmental projects, and social advocacy.	P6, P8
Policy Engagement & Debate	Some respondents actively participated in policy discussions on ASEAN issues such as the South China Sea dispute and non-interference policies.	P5, P8

Balancing Limited Exposure and Selective Engagement: Generation Z's Diverse Experiences with ASEAN Integration in Phnom Penh. The findings from both the quantitative survey and the qualitative key informant interviews (KII) offer a complementary view of Generation Z's experiences with ASEAN integration in Phnom Penh, providing a more comprehensive understanding of their level of engagement with ASEAN-related activities.

The quantitative survey reveals that Generation Z in Phnom Penh has limited direct experience with ASEAN integration. With an overall General Weighted Average of 2.56, categorized as "Very Little Experience," the data shows that respondents have had minimal practical exposure to ASEAN opportunities. The low scores in items such as traveling to other ASEAN countries (mean = 1.81) and interacting with people from other ASEAN countries (mean = 2.40) confirm that many young Cambodians have had very little personal involvement in the regional integration process. Even when it comes to tangible benefits like scholarships or participating in ASEAN-related events, the experiences reported are scarce, with most responses indicating little to no engagement.

However, the KII responses offer a different and more nuanced perspective, highlighting the rich, albeit somewhat selective, experiences of some young Cambodians. While the survey suggests limited exposure for the majority, the KII reveals that there are a number of respondents who have participated in ASEAN programs such as academic exchanges, leadership summits, and policy simulations. These participants (P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, P8) have engaged in hands-on ASEAN activities, gaining practical knowledge and forming cross-cultural connections through initiatives like student exchanges, ASEAN workshops, and environmental projects. This engagement often extends to interactions with peers from other ASEAN countries, which, while not universally experienced, highlights the potential for deeper involvement among some Cambodian youth.

For instance, KII participants shared experiences from academic exchanges and ASEAN simulations, where they engaged in discussions on regional issues, developed diplomatic skills, and formed a stronger sense of regional identity. These experiences, while not widespread across all

participants, demonstrate how ASEAN integration can provide valuable learning opportunities that enhance both personal and professional development.

Additionally, the KII responses indicate that some young people in Phnom Penh have taken leadership roles in ASEAN-affiliated initiatives, such as entrepreneurship programs, environmental advocacy, and social innovation projects. These initiatives underscore ASEAN's potential as a platform for youth-driven change, and they align with survey items that suggested a moderate level of experience in developing a sense of cultural and social identity as an ASEAN citizen (mean = 2.65) and improving attitudes toward ASEAN integration (mean = 2.74).

Despite these positive examples, both the quantitative and qualitative data highlight a common theme of limited accessibility to ASEAN-related programs. Several KII participants pointed out that many Cambodian youths are unaware of the available opportunities, echoing the survey's finding that engagement with ASEAN remains low for most respondents. This suggests that, while some young Cambodians benefit from ASEAN initiatives, broader outreach efforts are necessary to ensure inclusivity and equal access to ASEAN opportunities.

Themes Generated from KII's Answers

Participation in ASEAN Programs: (P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7, P8)

P1: "I have experienced attending a workshop which aimed to provide additional key knowledge about the Association of Southeast Asia."

P2: "I joined the workshop at the Royal Academy, speakers from ASEAN countries discussed AI and regional challenges."

P3: "I participated in education programs with Indonesian students to explore about their culture and research."

P4: "I interned at my university with an Indonesian classmate and it was an opportunity to collaborate with ASEAN peers."

P5: "I participated in an ASEAN conference on the South China Sea dispute as a Cambodian delegate."

P6: "I joined ASEAN programs as a social entrepreneur, representing Cambodia in South Korea."

P7: "My school organized cultural exchanges with Vietnamese students, fostering ASEAN connections."

P8: "I took part in a Model ASEAN Summit course, simulating diplomatic negotiations."

Academic & Cultural Exchange: (P3, P4, P6, P7, P8)

P3: "Working with Indonesian students helped me understand their culture and research perspectives."

P4: "My Indonesian classmate's courage to study in Cambodia showed ASEAN's educational integration."

P6: "Meeting social entrepreneurs from ASEAN countries taught me about regional innovations."

P7: "Exchanging traditions with Vietnamese students deepened my appreciation for ASEAN diversity."

P8: "The Model ASEAN Summit exposed me to collaborative problem-solving among member states."

ASEAN Simulation & Model Summits (P2, P5, P8)

P2: "In a class simulation, I acted as Cambodia's representative in an ASEAN meeting."

P5: "Debating the South China Sea dispute as a delegate highlighted ASEAN's consensus challenges."

P8: "The Model ASEAN Summit course taught me how delegates draft position papers and negotiate."

Workshops on ASEAN Issues: (P1, P2, P3, P7)

P1: "Workshops taught me about ASEAN's three pillars: political, economic, and socio-cultural integration."

P2: "A workshop on AI's regional impact featured speakers from multiple ASEAN countries."

P3: "ASEAN workshops emphasized collective action for regional stability."

P7: "I attended a workshop on ASEAN's role in global diplomacy beyond Southeast Asia."

Youth Leadership & Advocacy: (P6, P8)

P6: "As an eco-leader, I collaborated with ASEAN peers on climate resilience and circular economy projects."

P8: "Acting as a delegate in the Model ASEAN Summit honed my leadership in policy negotiation."

Policy Engagement & Debate: (P5, P8)

P5: "I challenged ASEAN's non-interference policy during debates on the Myanmar crisis."

P8: "Writing position papers for the Model ASEAN Summit sharpened my policy analysis skills."

In summary, the quantitative survey and KII results complement each other by providing both a broad overview and specific insights into the experiences of Generation Z in Phnom Penh regarding ASEAN integration. While the survey indicates limited practical experiences for most young people, the KII offers a more detailed look at the positive experiences of a subset of individuals who have actively engaged with ASEAN programs. Together, these findings suggest that although ASEAN integration has made an impact on some members of Generation Z, greater efforts are needed to increase awareness and accessibility, enabling more youth to benefit from regional cooperation and fostering a deeper sense of ASEAN identity.

Discussion

Experiences of Generation Z in Phnom Penh about ASEAN Integration

In answer to the research question of the study, "*What is the level of experiences of Generation Z in Phnom Penh about ASEAN integration?*", it can be surmised that the level of experiences of Generation Z in Phnom Penh about ASEAN integration is generally low, with an average score of 2.56, categorized as "Very Little Experience." Most respondents report minimal exposure to ASEAN-related activities such as travel, direct interaction with people from other ASEAN countries, and engagement with ASEAN opportunities like scholarships or job markets. However, there are moderate levels of experience in cultural learning, developing a sense of ASEAN identity, and improving attitudes towards ASEAN integration. While some individuals report richer experiences through participation in exchange programs, ASEAN simulations, and leadership initiatives, these are not widespread across the entire group.

The results indicate that, on average, Generation Z in Phnom Penh has limited practical engagement with ASEAN integration. The low scores in travel (1.81), interaction with people from other ASEAN countries (2.40), and participation in ASEAN events (2.20) suggest that many young people have not had direct, hands-on experiences with the benefits or opportunities offered by ASEAN integration. However, the moderate scores in areas such as cultural awareness (2.84) and developing an ASEAN-related identity (2.65) show that, while practical engagement is limited, there is a growing awareness and appreciation of ASEAN's cultural diversity and regional cooperation.

The results are consistent with previous studies that highlight a lack of deep engagement among Southeast Asian youth with regional integration efforts. According to the ASEAN Integration Report 2023 by the Institute for Democracy and Economic Affairs (IDEAS), youth in ASEAN countries often feel disconnected from regional initiatives due to limited access to programs and awareness. Similarly, studies by Thompson, Thianthai, and Thuzar (2018) emphasize that while youth show general awareness of ASEAN's goals, their practical experiences and direct involvement are minimal, much like the findings from this study. Theories of regional integration, such as the Intergovernmental Model Moravcsik (1993), which argue that integration often focuses on governmental and economic cooperation, may explain the gap in youth participation. While ASEAN countries are increasingly interlinked politically and economically, cultural and social integration among the youth remains peripheral, likely due to the lack of outreach or engagement in education and youth-specific programs.

Results bear some theoretical implications. These findings suggest that the theory of regional integration may require adaptation to emphasize youth engagement as a core aspect of integration, especially in terms of cultural and social dimensions. It also implies that ASEAN integration is not only about economic policies but must extend into the realm of youth education, awareness, and active participation.

Results also bear some practical implications. Practically, these results indicate that ASEAN-related programs should increase accessibility to young people in Phnom Penh. This might include more outreach efforts, targeted awareness campaigns, and creating platforms for youth to engage directly with ASEAN initiatives.

When it comes to policy-related implications, policy-makers in ASEAN countries, including Cambodia, need to prioritize youth involvement in ASEAN integration processes. Establishing more scholarships, internships, and cross-border educational programs will help empower young people and foster a stronger sense of ASEAN identity among Generation Z.

An unexpected finding related to Generation Z experience about ASEAN integration is the relatively high level of engagement in cultural awareness (mean = 2.84) despite the overall low experience with ASEAN integration. This anomaly could be explained by the rise in digital media and access to information about ASEAN through social networks, educational content, and entertainment. While practical engagement remains limited, cultural knowledge and awareness may be more easily attained through indirect channels such as online platforms, media, and informal learning environments.

Limitations and Future Research

This study was geographically limited to Phnom Penh and relied on convenience sampling. Thus, the findings may not reflect rural youth experiences, who may have even more limited access to ASEAN-related programs. The reliance on self-reported data also raises concerns about social desirability bias.

Future studies could expand to rural areas, explore longitudinal impacts of ASEAN exposure, or compare different ASEAN countries to better understand structural gaps in youth inclusion.

Conclusion

Generation Z in Phnom Penh reports very little experience with ASEAN integration. The majority of respondents have minimal exposure to ASEAN-related activities, including travel, direct interactions with ASEAN nationals, and opportunities like scholarships or job markets. While experiences related to cultural learning, developing an ASEAN identity, and forming positive attitudes towards ASEAN integration are more moderate, they are not universally shared. A smaller group of respondents reports richer experiences through participation in exchange programs, ASEAN simulations, and leadership initiatives, although these are not widespread. The findings suggest that Generation Z in Phnom Penh has limited direct experience with ASEAN integration. Despite recognizing some cultural benefits and developing a sense of regional identity, their exposure to practical ASEAN activities such as travel, scholarships, or regional job markets remains minimal. The study highlights the need for greater opportunities for youth engagement with ASEAN initiatives to enhance their practical experience and deepen their understanding of regional integration.

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Ethical Approval

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